

There is a scientific paper with a proof based on its own existence

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Abstract

This paper provides the proof of the statement given in the title.

Definition

Any scientific paper has property P if it contains a proof which is based on the existence of that paper.

The following statement is equivalent with statement given in the title.

Statement

There is a scientific paper with property P .

Proof

The present paper exists [1]. This proof uses the existence of a paper that contains it (look up the previous statement). Therefore this paper has property P . Q.E.D.

Acknowledgment

I would like to acknowledge René Descartes for the basic idea.

- [1] Milovan Šuvakov, *There is a scientific paper with a proof based on its own existence*, this one